

TRIGONOMETRIC AND HYPERBOLIC POINCARÉ, SOBOLEV AND HILBERT-PACHPATTE TYPE INEQUALITIES

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ABSTRACT. In this article based on trigonometric and hyperbolic type Taylor formulae we establish Poincaré, Sobolev and Hilbert-Pachpatte type inequalities of different kinds specific and general.

1. MAIN RESULTS

Our motivation comes from the classic [2]. We start with a collection of Poincaré type inequalities.

Theorem 1.1. *Let $f \in C^2([a, b], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f(a) = f'(a) = 0$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|f + f''\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (1)$$

Proof. Since $f(a) = f'(a) = 0$, by Corollary 3.4 of [1] we have

$$f(x) = \int_a^x (f''(t) + f(t)) \sin(x-t) dt, \quad (2)$$

$\forall x \in [a, b]$.

It follows by Hölder's inequality that

$$\begin{aligned} |f(x)| &\leq \int_a^x |f''(t) + f(t)| |\sin(x-t)| dt \leq \\ &\left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_a^x |(f'' + f)(t)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \leq \\ &\left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

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Hence

$$|f(x)|^q \leq \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}^q, \quad (4)$$

and

$$\int_a^b |f(x)|^q dx \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right) \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}^q. \quad (5)$$

We have proved that

$$\left(\int_a^b |f(x)|^q dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (6)$$

□

It follows

Theorem 1.2. *All as in Theorem 1.1. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sinh(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|f - f''\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (7)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.1 is omitted. It is based on Corollary 3.5 of [1]. □

We continue with

Theorem 1.3. *Let $f \in C^4([a,b], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f(a) = f'(a) = f''(a) = f'''(a) = 0$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sinh(x-t) - \sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|f - f''''\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (8)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.1 is omitted. It is based on Corollary 3.6 of [1]. □

It follows

Theorem 1.4. *Let $f \in C^4([a,b], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f(a) = f'(a) = f''(a) = f'''(a) = 0$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Also let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ with $\alpha\beta(\alpha^2 - \beta^2) \neq 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{|\alpha|\beta|\beta^2 - \alpha^2|} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\beta \sin(\alpha(x-t)) - \alpha \sin(\beta(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|f'''' + (\alpha^2 + \beta^2)f'' + \alpha^2\beta^2 f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (9)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.1 is omitted. It is based on Corollary 3.7 of [1]. □

Next comes

Theorem 1.5. *Let $f \in C^4([a,b], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f^{(i)}(a) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$; $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, $\alpha \neq 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq$$

$$\frac{1}{2|\alpha|^3} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(\alpha(x-t)) - \alpha(x-t)\cos(\alpha(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left\| f^{(4)} + 2\alpha^2 f'' + \alpha^4 f \right\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (10)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.1 is omitted. It is based on Corollary 3.8 of [1]. $\square$

We continue with

Theorem 1.6. *All as in Theorem 1.4. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{|\alpha||\beta||\beta^2 - \alpha^2|} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\alpha \sinh(\beta(x-t)) - \beta \sinh(\alpha(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left\| f^{(4)} - (\alpha^2 + \beta^2) f'' + \alpha^2 \beta^2 f \right\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (11)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.1 is omitted. It is based on Corollary 3.9 of [1]. $\square$

We also give

Theorem 1.7. *All as in Theorem 1.5. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{2|\alpha|^3} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\alpha(x-t)\cosh(\alpha(x-t)) - \sinh(\alpha(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left\| f^{(4)} - 2\alpha^2 f'' + \alpha^4 f \right\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (12)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.1 is omitted. It is based on Corollary 3.10 of [1]. $\square$

We make

Remark. *The following come from [1]. Let K denote $\mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$. For $c = (c_0, \dots, c_n) \in K^{n+1}$ with $c_n = 1$, let the n -th order linear differential operator*

$$D_c : C^n([a, b], K) \rightarrow C([a, b], K)$$

be defined by the formula

$$D_c(f) := c_n f^{(n)} + \dots + c_1 f' + c_0 f \quad (f \in C^n([a, b], K)).$$

Let $\omega_c \in C^n(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C})$ denote the unique solution of the initial value problem

$$D_c(\omega_c) = 0, \quad \omega_c^{(l)}(0) = \delta_{l, n-1} \quad (l \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}). \quad (13)$$

The function ω_c will be called the characteristic solution of $D_c(\omega) = 0$.

Define

$$(T_{a,c}f)(x) := \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(f^{(j)}(a) \sum_{i=0}^{n-1-j} c_{i+j+1} \omega_c^{(i)}(x-a) \right), \quad (14)$$

if $f^{(j)}(a) = 0, j = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, then

$$(T_{a,c}f)(x) = 0, \quad \forall x \in [a, b].$$

Theorem 1.8. ([1]) Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $c = (c_0, \dots, c_n) \in K^{n+1}$ with $c_n = 1$. Then for all $f \in C^n([a, b], K)$, $x \in [a, b]$, we have

$$f(x) = (T_{a,c}f)(x) + \int_a^x D_c(f)(t) \omega_c(x-t) dt. \quad (15)$$

If $f^{(j)}(a) = 0$, $j = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, then

$$f(x) = \int_a^x D_c(f)(t) \omega_c(x-t) dt, \quad (16)$$

$\forall x \in [a, b]$.

We give the following general Poincaré type inequality.

Theorem 1.9. All as in Remark 1 and $f^{(j)}(a) = 0$, $j = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then

$$\|f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\omega_c(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|D_c(f)\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (17)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.1 is omitted. It is based on Remark 1 and Theorem 1.8. $\square$

Next follow Sobolev type inequalities.

Theorem 1.10. All as in Theorem 1.1, $r > 0$. Then

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (18)$$

Proof. As in (3) we have

$$|f(x)| \leq \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (19)$$

and (by $r > 0$)

$$|f(x)|^r \leq \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}^r, \quad (20)$$

$\forall x \in [a, b]$.

Thus

$$\int_a^b |f(x)|^r dx \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right) \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}^r, \quad (21)$$

and

$$\left(\int_a^b |f(x)|^r dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f'' + f\|_{L_q([a,b])}, \quad (22)$$

proving the claim. $\square$

Theorem 1.11. All as in Theorem 1.2, $r > 0$. Then

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sinh(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f - f''\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (23)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.10 is omitted. $\square$

Theorem 1.12. *All as in Theorem 1.3, $r > 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sinh(x-t) - \sin(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f - f''''\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (24)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.10 is omitted. $\square$

Theorem 1.13. *All as in Theorem 1.4, $r > 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{|\alpha||\beta||\beta^2 - \alpha^2|} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\beta \sin(\alpha(x-t)) - \alpha \sin(\beta(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f'''' + (\alpha^2 + \beta^2)f'' + \alpha^2\beta^2 f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (25)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.10 is omitted. $\square$

Theorem 1.14. *All as in Theorem 1.5, $r > 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{2|\alpha|^3} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\sin(\alpha(x-t)) - \alpha(x-t)\cos(\alpha(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f^{(4)} + 2\alpha^2 f'' + \alpha^4 f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (26)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.10 is omitted. $\square$

Theorem 1.15. *All as in Theorem 1.6, $r > 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{|\alpha||\beta||\beta^2 - \alpha^2|} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\alpha \sinh(\beta(x-t)) - \beta \sinh(\alpha(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f^{(4)} - (\alpha^2 + \beta^2)f'' + \alpha^2\beta^2 f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (27)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.10 is omitted. $\square$

Theorem 1.16. *All as in Theorem 1.7, $r > 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \frac{1}{2|\alpha|^3} \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\alpha(x-t)\cosh(\alpha(x-t)) - \sinh(\alpha(x-t))|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|f^{(4)} - 2\alpha^2 f'' + \alpha^4 f\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (28)$$

Proof. It is omitted. $\square$

Theorem 1.17. *All as in Theorem 1.9, $r > 0$. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L_r([a,b])} \leq \left(\int_a^b \left(\int_a^x |\omega_c(x-t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{r}{p}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \|D_c(f)\|_{L_q([a,b])}. \quad (29)$$

Proof. It is omitted. $\square$

We continue with a collection of Hilbert-Pachappted inequalities.

Theorem 1.18. *Here $j = 1, 2$. Let $f_j \in C^2([a_j, b_j], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f_j(a_j) = f_j'(a_j) = 0$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then*

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sin(x_1 - t_1)|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sin(x_2 - t_2)|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq (b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2) \|f_1'' + f_1\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \|f_2'' + f_2\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (30)$$

Proof. As in (3) we have

$$|f_1(x_1)| \leq \left(\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sin(x_1 - t_1)|^p dt_1 \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|f_1'' + f_1\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])}, \quad (31)$$

$\forall x_1 \in [a_1, b_1]$,
and

$$|f_2(x_2)| \leq \left(\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sin(x_2 - t_2)|^q dt_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|f_2'' + f_2\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (32)$$

$\forall x_2 \in [a_2, b_2]$.

Hence we have

$$|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| \leq \left(\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sin(x_1 - t_1)|^p dt_1 \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sin(x_2 - t_2)|^q dt_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \|f_1'' + f_1\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \|f_2'' + f_2\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])} \leq \quad (33)$$

(using Young's inequality for $a, b \geq 0$, $a^{\frac{1}{p}} b^{\frac{1}{q}} \leq \frac{a}{p} + \frac{b}{q}$)

$$\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sin(x_1 - t_1)|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sin(x_2 - t_2)|^q dt_2}{q} \right] \|f_1'' + f_1\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \|f_2'' + f_2\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (34)$$

So far we have

$$\frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)|}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sin(x_1 - t_1)|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sin(x_2 - t_2)|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq \|f_1'' + f_1\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \|f_2'' + f_2\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}, \quad (35)$$

$\forall (x_1, x_2) \in [a_1, b_1] \times [a_2, b_2]$.

The denominator in (35) can be zero only when both $x_1 = a_1$ and $x_2 = a_2$.

Therefore we obtain (30), by integrating (35) over $[a_1, b_1] \times [a_2, b_2]$. $\square$

Theorem 1.19. *All as in Theorem 1.18. Then*

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sinh(x_1 - t_1)|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sinh(x_2 - t_2)|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq (b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2) \|f_1 - f_1''\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \|f_2 - f_2''\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (36)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.18 is omitted. $\square$

Theorem 1.20. Here $j = 1, 2$. Let $f_j \in C^4([a_j, b_j], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f_j^{(i)}(a_j) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sinh(x_1-t_1) - \sin(x_1-t_1)|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sinh(x_2-t_2) - \sin(x_2-t_2)|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq \frac{(b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2)}{4} \left\| f_1 - f_1^{(4)} \right\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \left\| f_2 - f_2^{(4)} \right\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (37)$$

Proof. As similar to Theorem 1.18 is omitted. □

Theorem 1.21. Here $j = 1, 2$. Let $f_j \in C^4([a_j, b_j], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f_j^{(i)}(a_j) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Also let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ with $\alpha\beta(\alpha^2 - \beta^2) \neq 0$. Then

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\beta \sin(\alpha(x_1-t_1)) - \alpha \sin(\beta(x_1-t_1))|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\beta \sin(\alpha(x_2-t_2)) - \alpha \sin(\beta(x_2-t_2))|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq \frac{(b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2)}{\alpha^2 \beta^2 (\beta^2 - \alpha^2)^2} \left\| f_1^{(4)} + (\alpha^2 + \beta^2) f_1'' + \alpha^2 \beta^2 f_1 \right\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \left\| f_2^{(4)} + (\alpha^2 + \beta^2) f_2'' + \alpha^2 \beta^2 f_2 \right\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (38)$$

Proof. It is omitted. □

Theorem 1.22. Here $j = 1, 2$. Let $f_j \in C^4([a_j, b_j], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, such that $f_j^{(i)}(a_j) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$, and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$; $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, $\alpha \neq 0$. Then

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\sin(\alpha(x_1-t_1)) - \alpha(x_1-t_1) \cos(\alpha(x_1-t_1))|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\sin(\alpha(x_2-t_2)) - \alpha(x_2-t_2) \cos(\alpha(x_2-t_2))|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq \frac{(b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2)}{4\alpha^6} \left\| f_1^{(4)} + 2\alpha^2 f_1'' + \alpha^4 f_1 \right\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \left\| f_2^{(4)} + 2\alpha^2 f_2'' + \alpha^4 f_2 \right\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (39)$$

Proof. It is omitted. □

Theorem 1.23. All as in Theorem 1.21. Then

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\alpha \sinh(\beta(x_1-t_1)) - \beta \sinh(\alpha(x_1-t_1))|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\alpha \sinh(\beta(x_2-t_2)) - \beta \sinh(\alpha(x_2-t_2))|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq \frac{(b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2)}{\alpha^2 \beta^2 (\beta^2 - \alpha^2)^2} \left\| f_1^{(4)} - (\alpha^2 + \beta^2) f_1'' + \alpha^2 \beta^2 f_1 \right\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \left\| f_2^{(4)} - (\alpha^2 + \beta^2) f_2'' + \alpha^2 \beta^2 f_2 \right\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (40)$$

Proof. It is omitted. □

Theorem 1.24. *All as in Theorem 1.22. Then*

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\alpha(x_1-t_1) \cosh(\alpha(x_1-t_1)) - \sinh(\alpha(x_1-t_1))|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\alpha(x_2-t_2) \cosh(\alpha(x_2-t_2)) - \sinh(\alpha(x_2-t_2))|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq$$

$$\frac{(b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2)}{4\alpha^6} \left\| f_1^{(4)} - 2\alpha^2 f_1'' + \alpha^4 f_1 \right\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])}$$

$$\left\| f_2^{(4)} - 2\alpha^2 f_2'' + \alpha^4 f_2 \right\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (41)$$

Proof. It is omitted. $\square$

We finish with

Theorem 1.25. *Let $j = 1, 2$. Here $f_j \in C^4([a_j, b_j], K)$, where $K = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$, and $f_j^{(i)}(a_j) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$. All the rest are as in Remark 1 and $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then*

$$\int_{a_1}^{b_1} \int_{a_2}^{b_2} \frac{|f_1(x_1)| |f_2(x_2)| dx_1 dx_2}{\left[\frac{\int_{a_1}^{x_1} |\omega_c(x_1-t_1)|^p dt_1}{p} + \frac{\int_{a_2}^{x_2} |\omega_c(x_2-t_2)|^q dt_2}{q} \right]} \leq$$

$$(b_1 - a_1)(b_2 - a_2) \|D_c(f_1)\|_{L_q([a_1, b_1])} \|D_c(f_2)\|_{L_p([a_2, b_2])}. \quad (42)$$

Proof. It is omitted. $\square$

Conclusion: We presented a set of very important analytical inequalities generated by some new trigonometric and hyperbolic Taylor formulae. That is a new important way in establishing inequalities.

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